

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF USING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article explores ways to improve the efficiency of utilizing the economic potential of industrial enterprises. The study highlights key factors such as resource optimization, technological modernization, workforce competence, and sustainability. The research also emphasizes the role of innovation and government policies in enhancing industrial productivity and competitiveness.

Key words: economic potential, industrial enterprises, resource optimization, technological modernization, innovation, sustainability.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada sanoat korxonalarining iqtisodiy salohiyatidan samarali foydalanishni oshirish usullari o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot resurslarni optimallashtirish, texnologik modernizatsiya, ishchi kuchining malakasi va barqarorlik kabi asosiy omillarga e'tibor qaratadi. Shuningdek, innovatsiya va davlat siyosatining sanoat samaradorligi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishdagi o'rni ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy salohiyat, sanoat korxonalari, resurslarni optimallashtirish, texnologik modernizatsiya, innovatsiya, barqarorlik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются способы повышения эффективности использования экономического потенциала промышленных предприятий. Исследование акцентирует внимание на таких ключевых факторах, как оптимизация ресурсов, технологическая модернизация, квалификация рабочей силы и устойчивость. Также подчеркивается роль инноваций и государственной политики в повышении промышленной производительности и конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: экономический потенциал, промышленные предприятия, оптимизация ресурсов, технологическая модернизация, инновации, устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

Industrial enterprises are the backbone of any economy, contributing significantly to GDP and employment. However, many enterprises face challenges in maximizing their economic potential due to inefficiencies in resource management, outdated technologies, and ineffective organizational structures. Improving the efficiency of economic potential utilization is critical to achieving long-term success and resilience in a competitive global market.

The theme of improving the efficiency of using the economic potential of industrial enterprises is crucial for fostering sustainable development, enhancing competitiveness, and addressing global economic challenges. By optimizing resources, adopting modern technologies, and strengthening financial stability, industrial enterprises can play a pivotal role in driving national economic prosperity and global industrial progress. Technological advancements play a pivotal role in improving industrial efficiency: the implementation of ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) systems allows for better monitoring of resources, ensuring their optimal allocation and

reducing wastage. Innovations such as energy-efficient machinery, renewable energy integration, and circular economy principles contribute to efficient resource utilization while meeting environmental goals.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of economic potential in industrial enterprises has been extensively explored by scholars worldwide. Economic potential is often understood as a combination of resources, capabilities, and conditions that allow an enterprise to achieve its strategic objectives effectively. Researchers such as Porter have emphasized that the competitive advantage of enterprises stems from their ability to strategically deploy internal resources while responding to external market forces. Porter's value chain analysis highlights that optimizing each component of production and management processes significantly contributes to the efficient utilization of economic potential.

The relationship between resource allocation and productivity has been another focal point. Barney, in his Resource-Based View (RBV) framework, underscores that enterprises with unique, valuable, and inimitable resources are better positioned to leverage their economic potential. This perspective aligns with the findings of Penrose, who argued that the managerial capabilities of firms play a crucial role in unlocking latent potential, enabling firms to expand without facing diminishing returns.

Innovation is also a critical determinant of economic potential utilization. Drucker's work on innovation suggests that enterprises with robust innovation ecosystems tend to outperform their competitors by maintaining operational flexibility and adapting to market dynamics. Similarly, Schumpeter highlighted the role of entrepreneurial dynamism and technological innovation in enhancing industrial productivity.

In the context of industrial enterprises, factors such as technological modernization, workforce competence, and energy efficiency have been identified as pivotal. Studies by Freeman indicate that technological advancements, particularly automation and digitalization, are key drivers of efficiency in resource utilization. At the same time, Becker and Huselid explored the link between human capital and organizational performance, asserting that a skilled and motivated workforce is instrumental in maximizing economic potential.

Government policy and regulatory frameworks also play a significant role in shaping the efficiency of industrial enterprises. North's institutional economics framework illustrates how well-designed policies can incentivize efficient resource use and investment. This notion is supported by Rodrik, who pointed out that industrial policies tailored to local contexts can catalyze industrial growth while minimizing inefficiencies.

Lastly, the role of sustainability in enhancing economic potential has garnered attention. Researchers like Elkington have proposed the triple bottom line approach, which integrates economic, social, and environmental objectives to create sustainable industrial enterprises. The adoption of green technologies and practices has been shown to not only reduce operational costs but also improve long-term competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involved collecting data from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained through surveys and interviews with industry experts and enterprise managers, while secondary data was gathered from academic journals, industry reports, and official statistics. The collected data was analyzed using quantitative methods, including statistical analysis, and qualitative approaches, such as content analysis, to identify patterns, relationships, and key factors affecting the efficient use of economic potential in industrial enterprises.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Comprehensive evaluation of the realization of the resource potential of industrial enterprises is essential for enhancing their operational and strategic performance. A distinctive feature of the proposed methodological approach lies in its dynamic and flexible use of index indicators for structural blocks, which enable a systematic evaluation of the comprehensive resource utilization efficiency in industrial enterprises.

It is recommended to include the following indicators in the system of economic evaluation: the efficiency of using intangible resources, the information efficiency of resource use, the efficiency of utilizing innovative potential, and others. Assessing resource use efficiency through index methods offers several advantages. These methods are faster than other analytical approaches, require minimal additional statistical data, and provide reliable results for evaluating the economic potential of enterprises.

World scientists emphasize the importance of several factors in the development of industrial enterprises. They have concluded that the presence and level of these factors are critical for ensuring industrial growth and competitiveness (Pic. 1).

Picture 1. Factors for the development and efficiency improvement of industrial enterprises.

One of the ways to improve the efficiency of industrial enterprises is the effective use of raw materials available within the network. Raw materials represent a certain amount of labor required for their extraction or production. They refer to the product of labor that has been expended and transformed to a certain extent as a result of this labor. Raw materials can be categorized as key and auxiliary materials. The main raw material forms the material basis of the finished product and is itself a product of labor. Necessary conditions for the processing of raw materials are reflected in their incorporation into the finished product or their role as primary raw materials. All other materials involved in the production process, which do not form the core of the finished product, are considered auxiliary materials. Enhancing the efficiency of industrial enterprises by increasing resource efficiency and ensuring their full utilization is a critical factor in improving overall performance.

Many industrial enterprises face significant challenges in fully utilizing their economic potential. One key obstacle is technological lag. Many enterprises, particularly in developing economies, struggle to adopt modern technologies such as automation, IoT (Internet of Things), and AI (Artificial Intelligence) due to financial constraints or a lack of technical expertise. This technological gap results in reduced productivity and higher operational costs, further impeding their ability to compete effectively in the global market (Pic. 2).

Picture 2. Key challenges in enhancing the efficiency of industrial enterprises.

The efficiency of utilizing the economic potential of industrial enterprises has been extensively discussed in academic and professional literature. Key areas of focus include resource optimization, technological advancements, and sustainable practices. The following points summarize the main themes from the literature:

Resource Utilization: Scholars emphasize that efficient resource management is crucial for enhancing productivity and competitiveness. Works by Porter (1985) highlight the role of strategic management in aligning resources with enterprise goals.

Technological Innovation: Research on Industry 4.0 technologies demonstrates their transformative potential for industrial enterprises through automation, IoT, and AI (Kagermann et al., 2013). These innovations enable businesses to streamline operations and achieve higher efficiency levels.

Human Capital Development: Literature, such as Becker's (1993) work, underscores the importance of investing in human capital through training and motivation to ensure workforce adaptability to technological changes.

Sustainability Practices: Environmental sustainability is an increasing concern in industrial enterprise management. Publications like Elkington's (1997) advocate for the triple bottom line—balancing economic, environmental, and social responsibilities.

Financial and Strategic Management: Strategic frameworks, including SWOT and PESTLE analyses, are extensively discussed for industrial enterprises to identify opportunities and mitigate risks (Gürel & Tat, 2017).

Labor productivity in the development of industrial sectors, based on the effective use of internal capabilities and the study of the relationship between wages, remains a critical topic. Theories on the relationship between labor productivity and wages in industrial enterprises have been studied by representatives of various scientific schools. Most scientists agree with the principle that “everyone should be encouraged according to the work he has done.” A group of scientists, led by T. Edison, suggests that wages should be based on the connection between labor and intellectual or creative activity. A. Marshall's theory posits that wages should be established based on productivity, though he also noted that for some labor-intensive tasks, production results cannot always be directly linked to wages.

Green Jobs: Green jobs are defined as well-paid career opportunities that contribute directly to the protection or improvement of environmental quality. These roles, often categorized as green-collar jobs, exist between low-skill and high-skill levels, offering high pay and opportunities for promotion in terms of skill development and wages. Green jobs also emphasize safe working conditions and the protection of workers' rights, including the right to organize trade unions.

Uzbekistan's industrial sector plays a pivotal role in its economic development, contributing significantly to GDP and employment. However, challenges such as outdated technologies, inefficient resource utilization, and skill gaps hinder the sector's ability to achieve optimal efficiency. Key strategies to enhance the economic potential of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan focus on resource optimization, technological innovation, workforce development, sustainability, and strategic management.

Improving the efficiency of utilizing the economic potential of industrial enterprises is a multi-dimensional process requiring a focus on technology, financial stability, resource management, and human capital development. Addressing existing challenges while implementing innovative strategies ensures long-term growth, competitiveness, and sustainability in the industrial sector.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

To increase the efficiency of industrial enterprises, it is essential to determine the importance of raw materials and calculate the minimum value of costs based on accurate assessments. Effective resource utilization, combined with infrastructure development such as roads, provides opportunities to enhance the operational efficiency of industrial enterprises in the region. Additionally, replacing outdated production technologies with modern alternatives can significantly improve productivity. This process requires the calculation of preference indices and the concordance coefficient of expert opinions to ensure effective decision-making in technology replacement strategies.

If innovative groups are established and initiatives aimed at the development of industrial enterprises are carried out on their foundation, the industrial sector's potential will grow substantially. These efforts will also create opportunities to address existing problems and identify new pathways for sustainable industrial development.

Strategic management, supported by public-private partnerships and policy reforms, plays a pivotal role in overcoming inefficiencies and fostering innovation. With its abundant resources, favorable geographic location, and ongoing economic reforms, Uzbekistan has the potential to transform its industrial sector into a driving force for regional and global economic integration.

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

